

**MODERN TECHNIQUES FOR RESTORING BONE DEFECTS IN THE ALVEOLAR
PART AND ALVEOLAR PROCESS OF THE JAWS IN PREPARATION FOR DENTAL
IMPLANTATION**

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Annotation

In modern dental practice, patients are increasingly planning to restore their teeth using dental implants. When a tooth is removed from its socket, the periodontal fibers are torn, which inevitably triggers the resorption of the cortical plate of the outer wall of the alveolus, the level of which depends on its width and the number of fibers it contains. In the frontal section of the jaws, the thickness of the outer wall of the alveolus occasionally reaches 1 mm and is subjected to almost complete lysis during tooth extraction. The data obtained as a result of a systematic retrospective analysis does not provide an adequate evidence base for determining the specific advantages of one method of surgical treatment of alveolar ridge atrophy of the upper jaw over other methods. Any technique should be selected in accordance with the individual anatomical features of the patient. The extent of surgical intervention depends on the severity of jawbone atrophy. It is of paramount importance to obtain research results in combination with concomitant diseases.

Keywords: Osteoplasty, alveolar part of the jaws, dental implantation

The positive or negative outcome of orthopedic treatment largely depends on the volume of bone tissue in the alveolar process. A lack of width leads to difficulties in performing dental implantation or makes it impractical without additional measures [7,11,17].

The patient's adaptation to orthopedic structures with a pronounced reduction in jaw volume due to their loose fixation is associated with serious problems and sometimes may not occur at all. Until recently, such patients underwent orthopedic treatment many times, and in some cases, all the assistance provided was unsuccessful. However, in such cases, restoration of the atrophied alveolar ridge is now indicated [2,4,10,13,16].

Yamurkova N.F. and co-authors (2015) note in their works that volumetric restoration using developed methods of surgical treatment of pronounced atrophy of the alveolar ridge of the upper jaw contributes to the creation of sufficient conditions for the installation of dental implants and further orthopedic restoration of the dentition with masticatory function. Among other techniques, the authors highlight G-shaped autograft plastic surgery, reconstruction of defects with local bone tissue (sandwich plastic surgery, sliding bone fragment method, intercortical osteotomy and bone tissue splitting in the defect area).

In his research paper (2011), Razmyslov A. V. pointed out that the use of bone materials in dental practice enhances osteogenesis and makes it possible to create a bone matrix of new bone tissue of optimal density within 6 to 12 months.

An increase in the bone volume of the alveolar process of the upper jaw (sinus lifting) with the complex use of osteoplastic materials, resorbable membranes, and autogenous bone chips is characterized by an early and significant increase in the density of the formed bone tissue [1,3,11].

In alternative works, Kozlov L. (2015) recommends complex anti-osteoporotic therapy with bisphosphonates in combination with calcium and vitamin D3 preparations for atrophy of the alveolar processes of the jaws with reduced bone density, which leads to normalization of the trabecular bone architecture.

Scherchkov S.V. (2013) proposed an improved variation of the autogenous bone grafting technique similar to the veneer technique — through osteoperforation of the autograft and recipient site — to increase the predictability of implant treatment in patients with alveolar ridge atrophy. This modification with delayed installation of dental implants makes it possible to perform orthopedic treatment within 8 months, and the technique itself is indicated for bone widths of at least 3 mm and cortical layer thicknesses of no more than 1.5 mm.

Distraction osteogenesis does not require bone grafting, suturing of the donor site, or additional intervention to correct mucogingival attachment. Therefore, this method leads to fewer postoperative complications compared to other regenerative interventions [3,5,9,12].

However, when using this technique in the long term after vertical distraction of the bone callus, bone resorption was observed. Another disadvantage of this method is that it only allows for vertical regeneration.

Malanchuk V.A. (2002) proposed an alternative treatment method. After tooth extraction, the mucoperiosteal flap of the alveolar process is detached from the vestibular side and mobilized. With the double window technique, the Schneiderian membrane of the maxillary sinus can be mobilized from both the medial and distal windows, after which bone material is introduced. Endoscopic sinus lifting eliminates most of the disadvantages inherent in the traditional maxillary sinus procedure, avoids scarring of the mucous membrane, reduces blood loss, and preserves local blood microcirculation. This method involves restoring the integrity of the oral mucosa while simultaneously eliminating the defect in the alveolar bone tissue and creating the necessary volume of bone tissue for further rehabilitation of patients using delayed dental implantation.

Taking the results of these studies into account in the future may make it possible to monitor the bone regeneration process during surgical treatment of alveolar ridge atrophy and significantly increase its predictability.

In cases of quantitative and qualitative bone tissue deficiency in the alveolar ridge, certain interventions may be required to increase the volume and density of the jawbone. Depending on the location of the defect, the most common techniques for increasing bone volume are: - filling the bone defect with synthetic or autogenous bone material, including during implantation; - Schneiderian membrane elevation surgery - sinus lifting; - guided bone regeneration using bone autografts, synthetic bone substitutes in combination with resorbable and non-resorbable membranes [6,7,9].

Depending on the method of production, all bone grafting materials are divided into four groups: - autogenous (obtained from the patient's own tissues); - allogeneic (obtained from the tissues of another individual of the same biological species, i.e., from another person); - xenogeneic (from tissues of another biological species, i.e., animals); - alloplastic, i.e., artificially produced. Autogenous bone graft materials combine osteoconductive and osteoinductive properties; allogeneic materials have a predominantly osteoconductive effect, but may also have osteoinductive properties;

xenogenic and alloplastic materials are characterized only by osteoconductivity. Autogenous bone is currently considered the most effective bone grafting material, a kind of “gold standard” in bone grafting. The donor site for harvesting an autologous bone graft can be either extraoral (iliac crest, rib, tibia, fibula, skull bones) or intraoral (external oblique line, retromolar region, chin). In addition, it is also possible to use bone chips that are formed during the formation of the implant bed, collecting them with a device that attaches to a surgical suction device called a “bone trap.” The disadvantages of autotransplantation include trauma during graft harvesting and the risk of uncontrolled resorption. Therefore, it is justified to search for the optimal type of preserved bone tissue of allogeneic origin. The highest osteoplastic efficacy has been determined for demineralized lyophilized allograft bone matrix. It contains mostly collagen, non-collagenous bone matrix proteins, bone growth factors, and has both osteoconductive and osteoinductive properties. Among xenogenic materials, the most widely used are biogenic hydroxyapatite and deproteinized bovine bone (Bio-Oss preparation), as well as sulfated glycosaminoglycans obtained from the cartilage tissue of cattle and shark fins. Among alloplastic materials, the most studied are “Paris plaster” (calcium sulfate), calcium triphosphate [Ca₃(P₀₄)₂], and “Biosittal”. For volumetric augmentation, it is recommended to combine all alloplastics and xenoplastics with autologous bone and use them as a filling substance under a barrier membrane. The idea of combining different bone-plastic materials has found great and effective clinical application. One of the newest areas of research is the development and practical use of various bone growth stimulators, TGF-β, which have the most pronounced osteoinductive effect. These include a group of bone morphogenetic proteins obtained from bulls that stimulate osteogenesis. In addition, plasma depleted of red and white blood cells by centrifugation and enriched with platelets is used in practical surgery. It contains several bone growth factors and promotes the formation of more mature and organized bone tissue around the implant. Platelet-depleted blood plasma takes on the appearance of a sticky film and can be used as a barrier membrane. Of the arsenal of augmentation methods frequently used in dental implantology, the most advanced method of reparative osteogenesis is considered to be the technique of guided bone tissue regeneration using various types of separating barrier membranes. Later, A. Melcher and G. Dreyer (1962) added a couple more points to the above conditions: prevention of blood clot ingrowth into surrounding soft tissues; control of blood clot size and prevention of pressure from covering soft tissues during scar formation. The above provisions are implemented using a membrane technique aimed at creating a biological and mechanical barrier between the bone defect and the surrounding soft tissues to prevent fibroblasts and epithelium from entering the bone defect area. There are two types of barrier membranes. Non-resorbable membranes are often made of polytetrafluoroethylene and fixed with titanium screws. They must be removed 5-6 months after the operation. These include titanium meshes and “Gore-Tex”, “Gytoplast”, and “Tefogen” membranes. Absorbable membranes remain sufficiently dense for 1-2 months and are completely resorbed by the tissues after another 1-2 months. In most cases, they are made of xenogeneic collagen, as well as resorbable synthetic polymers such as Vicryl. Examples include Gore-Resolut XT, Epi Guide, Osteoplast, and Parodoncoll. No repeat surgery is required to remove them. Bone wound healing under the membranes occurs through primary tension using mobilization of the mucoperiosteal flap to relieve tension. The disadvantages of this method include the duration of treatment (6-8 months), exposure of the membrane with elements of inflammation in the area of surgical intervention, and the need for repeat surgery to remove non-resorbable membranes. There are two main approaches to implantation in this clinical

case: - bypassing the maxillary sinus with implantation in the border zone; - increasing the height by reducing the volume of the sinus. Favorable conditions for the first technique are rare. Moreover, implantation in the maxillary tuberosity area carries a significant risk due to the loose bone structure in this area. A widely used method is sinus lifting surgery, which involves raising the floor of the maxillary sinus. The closed method is used when the height of the alveolar ridge is less than 5-7 mm, if it needs to be increased by 2-3 mm. Through the bone bed formed for the implant in the projection of the sinus floor, the wall of the sinus floor is slightly broken with osteotomes and displaced deeper. The bone defect is filled from the inside with osteoplastic material, and then the implant is installed. The idea of the open technique is to form an oval bone fragment on the vestibular wall of the maxillary sinus and rotate it inward to form a new level of the sinus floor. An important condition is the detachment and preservation of the integrity of the Schneiderian membrane [7,10,14,15]. The resulting space is filled with bone graft material in the form of blocks and chips (ground autogenous bone is also possible), and the opening on the outer wall of the upper jaw is closed with a barrier membrane. Implant placement using the open method can be performed either simultaneously with sinus lifting or delayed until bone tissue regeneration and restoration of the alveolar ridge height (6-8 months). For alveolar ridge augmentation, in addition to autologous bone transplantation, the use of bone grafting materials, and guided bone regeneration, surgical techniques have also been developed for splitting the alveolar ridge with special instruments — distractors, when implants are inserted into the gap formed during the cutting of bone tissue, and the spaces between them are filled with osteoplastic material. In cases of extensive bone tissue atrophy in the distal parts of the lower jaw due to the close location of the mandibular canal, a method for lateralization of the inferior alveolar nerve has been developed. The purpose of this intervention is to create conditions for the installation of implants over the entire volume of the lower jaw bone. During this operation, after making an incision along the top of the alveolar part, the mucoperiosteal flap is widely detached from the vestibular surface of the lower jaw, after which an osteotomy is performed along the outer oblique line in the projection of the mandibular canal and the bone is carefully ground down from its vestibular wall. The inferior alveolar nerve is isolated and retracted, and a bed for the implants is formed. The space in the bone tissue after implant placement is filled with osteoplastic material, and the nerve trunk is placed in its previous position under the mucoperiosteal flap, taking the utmost care to avoid nerve trauma. In addition to the above methods, for different degrees of alveolar bone atrophy, the method of vinirio osteoplasty is used for dental implantation, the essence of which is to take an autogenous bone graft from extraoral areas, most often from the iliac crest, and placing it on the atrophied alveolar ridge, in which compact osteotomy is performed beforehand. The bone block is fixed with titanium screws. This technique makes it possible to increase both the width and height of the future implantation area in the corresponding section of the jaw. Despite this, there has been a growing number of supporters of immediate implantation in recent years. A number of articles have demonstrated successful results of prosthetics on implants installed in a single stage with bone grafting, both with autografts and bioplastic materials. The frequency of successful implantation in the long term is 87%. However, the degree of resorption can reach 50% within 5 years, with the condition of the graft being unpredictable. Despite this, the undeniable advantage of immediate implantation is the reduction in surgical intervention and the time required for final prosthetics [6,8,14,17].

Currently, autografts and allografts are used to increase both the height and width of the alveolar ridge of the lower jaw. The method of placing a bone block on the frontal part of the ridge makes it possible to reduce the interalveolar distance, but, on the other hand, often requires additional soft tissue plastic surgery and is associated with the need to refrain from wearing a prosthesis for a long time. Based on this, in cases of severe atrophy of the lower jaw (less than 5 mm in height), it was proposed to install a combined auto-allotransplant on the lower surface of the lower jaw. In the postoperative period, the patient is able to use a removable prosthesis until it becomes possible to install intraosseous implants. In addition to bone blocks, crushed bone can be used in combination with a membrane to create a targeted bone regeneration effect that holds the graft in place, prevents premature resorption of the bone graft, and creates a barrier to the growth of fibrous and connective tissue into the recipient area. Teflon and polytetrafluoroethylene can be used as non-resorbable materials. The disadvantage of non-resorbable membranes is the need for secondary surgical intervention to remove them (Kulakov A.A. et al., 2000), but otherwise, as shown by a randomized controlled study, both types of membranes are equally effective in providing guided bone regeneration in cases of reliable initial fixation.

The main drawback of the topical application of autogenous and allogeneic bone grafts is their high rate of subsequent resorption. In this regard, the principle of upward advancement of the alveolar ridge of the lower jaw has been proposed. The technique of horizontal osteotomy of the frontal section of the mandible with rotation of the upper segment, developed by Barros Saint Posteur J., was then refined by the use of an autograft from the iliac crest or rib bone, placed between the body of the mandible and the cut-off fragment of the alveolar process, and named “sandwich” osteotomy or “inlay grafting” [9,11,14,16].

For local widening of the alveolar part of the lower jaw, techniques for splitting bone plates (similar to the “green twig” technique, Rendo B. et al., 1997) with simultaneous implant placement have been proposed. The bone tissue of the narrow alveolar ridge is gradually broken and spread apart using a chisel to form a bed for the implants. The surgical defect creates ideal conditions for bone tissue regeneration. If the splitting area is large and the implant or cortical plates are not very stable, titanium mesh, autogenous bone, or alloplastic material is used as a filler for stabilization.

Xenotransplantation is the transplantation of animal tissue. Xenotransplantation is currently widely used in clinical practice, as osteoplastic materials are often made using animal collagen matrices. This method has an excellent legal basis, reduces surgery time, and causes no additional trauma. The disadvantages of this method are the possibility of an immune response in the body and the uncontrolled rate of material resorption — premature dissolution without replacement of the defect with newly formed bone [9,15].

Based on the above material, the data obtained as a result of a systematic retrospective analysis do not provide the necessary evidence base to determine the clear advantages of one method of surgical treatment of maxillary alveolar ridge atrophy over alternative methods. Each of the above techniques should be selected in accordance with the anatomical features of the patient. The extent of surgical intervention depends on the level of jawbone atrophy. It is particularly important to obtain research results in conjunction with concomitant diseases.

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